

Changing Perception of Costomers Towords Fast Food : A Comparative Analysis with Special Reference to Pizza Hut and Domino's Pizza

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Abstract:- Comparative analysis is a way to look two or more similar things to see how they different and same. When business wants to grow a comparative analysis can give them information. With increase in disposable income and changing attitude the demand of fast-food items is rising. Customer perception can change depends on service quality dimensions, accessibility, offers and verities they find in and around. This study involves in primary and secondary data, this study is going to help the areas of improvement needed so that they can attract a greater number of customers and factors to be taken care in order to cater better to their customers.

Keywords:- Perception, Customer, Comparative Analysis, Service Quality, Dimentions, Improvement, Service Quality, Customer Satisfaction.

I. INTRODUCTION

With increasing disposable income and changing attitude, the exposure to various global cuisines or local delicacies, the Indian customers are always ready to taste the both. The demand for various fast-food items is rising in India. The most popular of them is Pizza. The major in Indian Pizza industry are Pizza Hut and Domino's pizza.

The study involves comparison of two fast food joints Pizza Hut and Domino's Pizza. The goal of this study is to compare these two joints under different factors such as customers perception, service quality dimensions, accessibility, offers and varieties in the menu provided by these joints.

II. STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

The intention of the study is to compare between the two fast food restaurants Pizza hut and Dominos in terms of their products, services and to provide suggestions for improvement of them in pizza hut & to find out the satisfaction level of the consumers.

III. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To understand the level of customer satisfaction towards the Pizza Hut and Dominos in Davangere city
- To analyze the service quality offered
- To understand the tangible elements preferred by the customers
- To understand the perception of customers toward both brands

IV. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The study aims to understand satisfaction of the customer toward these joints and will also focus on understanding what factors influence the customer to visit these joints and to analyze their preferences and perceptions. Also, the study aims to understand the different dimensions of serviceability at these joints and compares these joints under these criteria. The study focuses on the customers under the variables like age, gender, research design.

V. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research methodology is a way to systematically solve a problem; it may be understood as a science of study where the research is done scientifically. It includes various steps that are generally adopted by a researcher in study his research problem. This study describes the methods applied for the study in detail. The methodology of the study includes

VI. LITRATURE REVIEW

A. Dr. P K Vimala (2020)

As per the market research conducted one of the major customers of pizza are Indians. Dominos and Pizza hut are one amongst the best brands having highest shares in market. The study intends to understand the preference of customers towards purchasing of pizzas and also to know about their patterns of consumption and opinions. This study at the comparison between the Domino's and Pizza Hut consumers towards their preference, likability towards services and their affordability. This study is useful to entice further strategies for improving customer indulgence with Pizza. Moreover, it will enable the marketers also to improve their products based upon the preference of the customers.

B. Kirti Dutta (2008)

The psychological factors such as customers attitudes, behavioral intentions, and involvement in connection to Green practices are investigated by the study. The cultural differences between the countries India and US are considered. These psychological factors are measured by health, environmental and social concerns. Also, the study analyses how the customers willingness to pay for green practices are influenced by these factors. Results reveal that intentions, attitudes, and involvement in green practices of customers of two different countries are distinct.

C. Dr. Nida Malik (2022)

This study examines the different factors that affects the perception of youths in prioritizing their choices and interests towards different international and domestic outlets offering fast food items. The researchers conducted paired T- test method to calculate standard deviation for each pair of question asked individually for respondents. Further, the researchers have also analyzed paired sample correlation in order to establish relationship between the selected variables on the basis of taste, quality, price, pattern and other relevant factors with reference to the objectives of research.

D. Sungil Lee (2012)

This paper has two purposes, the first one is to identify the key actions that made Pizza Hut Korea to come out of decline in sales and profits for nine years. The second purpose is to gain deeper insight to some turnaround strategies of Pizza Hut Korea, such as customer lifetime value and return on marketing investment which made them to succeed.

E. Anitam Goyal (2007)

This study was conducted to identify and examine the importance of several factors that influence youthful Indian customers to choose fast food restaurants. The study involves multivariate statistical approaches to determine importance of different factors that influence young customers fast food restaurant choices. The quality of fast-food outlet, consumption patterns, effects of nutritional values of food and hygiene was examined by the scientists.

VII. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

➤ *Chi-Square Test*

Table 1 Exhibit the relationship between occupation and frequency of visits to Pizza Hut

<i>Occupation</i>	<i>Weekly</i>	<i>Monthly</i>	<i>Occasionally</i>	<i>Total</i>
Student	08	20	20	48
Businessmen	01	03	03	07
Employee	06	05	15	26
Housewife	03	07	09	19
Total	18	35	47	100

$$\text{Chi square value } X^2 = \sum \frac{(O-E)^2}{E} = 4.0589$$

$$\text{Degree of freedom} = (\text{row1}) (\text{Column1}) = (4-1) (3-1) = 6$$

$$\text{Significance level} = 0.05$$

$$X^2 \text{ Tabular value} = 12.59$$

$$X^2 \text{ calculated value} < X^2 \text{ Tabular value}$$

➤ *Interpretation*

In the above analysis the calculated value (4.0589) is lower than the table value (12.59) at the level of significance (5%). Hence, there is a significant relationship between the occupation of the respondents and their frequency of visit to the Pizza Hut.

VIII. FINDINGS

- Majority of respondents presume that they are influenced by the friends to visit these joints, followed by the television ads
- Most of the responders said Pizza Hut gives more convenient offers to the customers when compared to dominos
- Maximum number of the respondents considered dining out at these joints than home delivery and most of them considered dining out at Dominos
- Majority of the responders provided higher ratings for taste of Dominos when compared to Pizza hut
- Most of the respondents says that Dominos offers wide range of varieties in its menu
- Maximum number of the respondents said Dominos is more Hygienic compare to pizza Hut
- Majority of the customers are dissatisfied with the pricing of Pizza Hut and customization of pizza
- Most of the responders are satisfied with home delivery services of pizza hut
- Maximum number of respondents said that Parking facility is the most important factor to visit the store
- Majority of the respondents presume that Pizza Hut provides rapid dine-in services

IX. CONCLUSION

Pizza Hut has become one among the well-established fast-food restaurants in Davangere by providing a convenient offer and rapid dine in services to the customers. Although, when compared with Domino’s Pizza, it is found that majority of customers prefer Domino’s over pizza hut due to various aspects. Henceforth, Pizza hut should try to attract more number of customers by focusing on their promotional activities and would try to improve the taste and range of varieties of their menu. They could also focus on improvising the customization of Pizza’s. Also, the joint would prioritize over hygiene and lowering the prices of their offerings so as to gain more customers. The joint also lacks the proper parking facility by availing proper parking may increase the visits of customer to the joint as the customers feel it’s the crucial factor for visit to these joints.

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